

Emerging locomotion behavior by maximizing entropy-based information metrics

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Abstract

The resilience and flexibility of intelligent robotic solutions that are currently being developed are still insufficient, despite the dramatic rate of innovation in robotics and artificial intelligence. Their comparison with the naturally evolved intelligent physical agents that we can observe in nature (such as animals and plants) still shows enormous gaps in terms of adaptivity, dexterity and flexibility. We believe that to get robotic platforms that can truly function well in complex open-ended real-world applications, we need a paradigm change from the top-down ‘Cartesian’ (assuming a neat division in between mind and body) mechatronic paradigm to a deeply bioinspired paradigm leveraging on morphological computation and emergence. Although learning techniques are helpful, real-time learning from data-rich time series, interaction with an unstructured environment, and collaboration with humans-who then learn alongside the intelligent service robots-needs novel algorithms and systems. The main thesis is that while “computing” is a feature of all material systems, intelligence and meaning are created by synchronization processes among networks of independent agents that are “situated” in their surroundings. Investigating the primary unresolved issues in the field of evolutionary emergent information processing in multibody (rigid, compliant, or hybrid) systems is the goal of our research project.

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Emerging locomotion behavior by maximizing entropy-based information metrics

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Abstract—The resilience and flexibility of intelligent robotic solutions that are currently being developed are still insufficient, despite the dramatic rate of innovation in robotics and artificial intelligence. Their comparison with the naturally evolved intelligent physical agents that we can observe in nature (such as animals and plants) still shows enormous gaps in terms of adaptivity, dexterity and flexibility. We believe that to get robotic platforms that can truly function well in complex open-ended real-world applications, we need a paradigm change from the top-down ‘Cartesian’ (assuming a neat division in between mind and body) mechatronic paradigm to a deeply bioinspired paradigm leveraging on morphological computation and emergence. Although learning techniques are helpful, real-time learning from data-rich time series, interaction with an unstructured environment, and collaboration with humans—who then learn alongside the intelligent service robots—needs novel algorithms and systems. The main thesis is that while “computing” is a feature of all material systems, intelligence and meaning are created by synchronization processes among networks of independent agents that are “situated” in their surroundings. Investigating the primary unresolved issues in the field of evolutionary emergent information processing in multibody (rigid, compliant, or hybrid) systems is the goal of our research project.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics has recently gained many capabilities for being effective and supportive to people within various contexts and applications, even if confined in structured environments and controlled conditions. As soon as these robots have to face a more unpredicted and dynamically-changing environment, their performance is more likely hindered in terms of adaptability, and their (centralized) control should become much more complex to cope with these unstructured situations. In nature, complex collective behaviors (and consequently adaptability) often emerge from much simpler decentralized procedures and subtask execution.

Emergent behavior is much desirable in swarms of robots (or robots made by “swarms of modules/agents”) in which many peer subsystems interact, each executing its own tasks with its own algorithms, concurring to the final requested cooperation and producing a sort of collective intelligence. One of the possible way to steer the emergence of this collective intelligence consists in the maximization of some metrics of information about the robot, the environment and the mutual interaction between them (how robot actions

affect the environment which is in turn perceived back by the robot itself).

An interesting example of emergent behavior in a robotic application is the Snakebot [1], which shows a self-organization of the behaviors of a snake-like robotic platform emerging from the maximization of some information metrics. To this aim, Lie Groups were exploited to reduce the computational burden of information-driven self-organization [2], expanding upon previous work [3], [4], [5]. The combination of concepts from self-organization (i.e. emergence) of intelligent behaviors and morphological computation can lead to the design of relatively ‘simple’ robust controllers for complex structures, more flexible and able to adapt to the environment and cope with dynamic changes. In our research, we are working to make this robotic self-organization resting on the maximization of suitable information metrics [6], [7], and by driving the evolution through a proper learning approach. With respect to Tanev and Prokopenko’s work [8], we consider a WormBot, inspired by their Snakebot, and similar to [9] we implement deep reinforcement learning methods to improve the sensorimotor coordination of the WormBot and its locomotion behaviors.

We believe that our approach could help to disclose the relation between the dynamics of an embodied agent and its information processing capabilities, in the spirit of [10].

II. SYSTEM SETUP AND METHODOLOGY

Designing locomotion controllers for complex robots is challenging, especially when accurate models are not available[9]. A particularly interesting metrics is the predictive information, I_p [11]. Expressed in equation 1, the Predictive information quantifies how much knowledge of the past of a time series helps us predict its future. By definition, it is the mutual information between the random variables’ “past” and “future” in the series. Intuitively, this means we measure how much observing past values reduces our uncertainty about future values. If a series has clear patterns or memory, then past observations carry useful clues about what comes next, so the predictive information is large. If the series is completely random (no correlations), then knowing the past gives no advantage, and the predictive information is zero. Locomotion is inherently sequential and dynamic actions taken now (like joint angles or muscle activations) influence what happens in the next few moments (e.g., body orientation, foot placement, balance). Predictive information measures how much of that future behavior is *already contained* in the past and current observations. This could be useful, as efficient locomotion often appears

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to rely on rhythmic, repeatable movement patterns (such as walking gaits). Predictive information may help identify components of the system's state that exhibit *predictable structure*, potentially including cyclic motor patterns.

$$I_p = I(x_{t-\tau+1}^{t+1}; x_{t-\tau}^t) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{\tau=1}^T H(x_{t+1-\tau}) + H(x_{t+1-\tau}|x_{t-\tau}) \quad (1)$$

In our work we addressed a simple embodiment, dealing with a worm-like robot, made of many different physical modules. Our primary goal was to understand if and to what extent an information metrics could aid the development of suitable locomotion gaits, given a series of situated cooperating agents (the modules composing the WormBot). We first implemented an architecture similar to those proposed in Tanev's Snakebot [1] and first of all tried to reproduce and validate his work, to update it to the new technologies and computing capabilities, and to make the approach more effective and efficient. We have developed a different approach that gave improved and interesting results. Both are described in the following subsections II and III.

A. WormBot I - evolutionary information-driven emerging behaviour

The worm-like robot is modeled as a series of 15 spheres, each with 0.3 *m* radius and 0.6 *kg* mass, connected among them through universal joints with axes along the *z* and *x* directions, respectively. Initially, the robot is stretched along the *y* axis. Each sphere is regarded as a single 'agent' able to move its own joint and interacting with the other companions to build up the overall worm-like robot. The objective is to obtain an emergent consistent motion for the worm-like structure in a distributed manner, by just allowing each agent (sphere) to control its own motion. This control is obtained through the maximization of some entropy-based information metrics, such as the transfer entropy (also known as information flow) or the predictive information. The first one adds to the symmetry of the mutual information (whenever applied to time series analysis) a sort of 'flow direction', allowing to study the relation between two stochastic variables *X* and *Y*, discerning which one influences the other; the transfer entropy is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} TE &= h_2 - h_1 = \\ &= -\sum_{x_{n+1}, x_n, y_n} p(x_{n+1}, x_n, y_n) \log p(x_{n+1}|x_n) + \\ &+ \sum_{x_{n+1}, x_n, y_n} p(x_{n+1}, x_n, y_n) \log p(x_{n+1}|x_n, y_n) = \\ &= \sum_{x_{n+1}, x_n, y_n} p(x_{n+1}, x_n, y_n) \log p\left(\frac{x_{n+1}|x_n, y_n}{x_{n+1}|x_n}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where h_1 is the amount of additional information needed to represent the next observation of one of the two systems (i.e. entropy rate), while h_2 is the same quantity assuming that *x* is independent of *y*.

On the other hand, the predictive information (also known as excess entropy) quantifies the possibility to predict a future value in a time series, knowing the series past values.

Note that for a random series this quantity is equal to zero, while for Markov processes it is equivalent to the mutual information between the current and next measured values, as expressed by:

$$I(X_{t+\tau}; X_t) = \left\langle \log \frac{p(x_{t+\tau}, x_t)}{p(x_{t+\tau})p(x_t)} \right\rangle = \left\langle \log \frac{p(x_{t+\tau}|x_t)}{p(x_{t+\tau})} \right\rangle \quad (3)$$

We exploited a classic Genetic Programming (GP) strategy to obtain a population of many generations. We defined base primitive functions that are combined in more complex ways during the simulation to obtain the overall motion command for the WormBot. We introduced the following primitives: $\sin(\cdot)$, $\cos(\cdot)$, $+$, $-$, $*$ and *protDiv* : (*a/b*; if *b* == 0 return 1). A further function, called ADF (Automatically Defined Function) is included, generated with the previously listed primitives, exploited as well as another primitive. All these functions, having the timestamp and the joint number as arguments, are employed to generate two commands, one for each axis of each universal joint. Tanev made the assumption that motion on the two axes is somehow synchronized imposing the same generated function in both directions; we relaxed this hypothesis imposing completely uncorrelated functions in our system.

For each time step and each joint, the results of these two functions are evaluated and sent to the dynamics simulator as joint input commands. This procedure is iterated for a number of different individuals in the population and, after that all the pre-defined number of timestamps has been executed, the fitness function of each individual is evaluated. The fitness is built upon two different criteria: i) traveled distance (in a vectorial sense); ii) correlation entropy. We then simulate the best individual, selected according to these criteria. At the end of each generation (i.e. after obtaining the results for all the individuals) we perform genetic operations such as selection, mutation and crossover.

B. WormBot II - information-driven learning

The original architecture relied on predefined primitive functions, such as sine and cosine, which inherently imposed oscillatory or periodic behavior on the system. We relaxed this assumption and we replaced this setup with a deep reinforcement learning framework that learns locomotion policies for the entire structure. This approach operates without prior knowledge of effective functions and without the use of low-level motion generators such as central pattern generators (CPGs) [12]. Instead, the learning process is guided solely by the maximization of the previously defined information-theoretic metrics.

System overview: The new setup, WormBot II, is a modular, worm-like robot consisting of 9 spherical segments, connected by simulated universal joints, implemented using pairs of perpendicular hinge joints and small auxiliary bodies. We reduced the number of bodies to speed up the simulation process and reduce the search space. This configuration results in a total of 16 controllable joints. The joint positions directly define the agent's action space, with

Fig. 1: Block scheme of the WormBot II architecture.

the policy output specifying target positions for each joint at every control step. Each joint is then controlled in position by a low-level PD controller. The system is implemented and simulated in the MuJoCo physics engine [13], with training performed using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm [14], as implemented in the Stable-Baselines3 (SB3) library [15].

Reward shaping: Each training episode has a fixed length of 1000 time steps. During each episode, as shown in equation 4, the reward function combines two key objectives:

- *Locomotion reward* r_{loc} , encoded as the forward velocity of the WormBot at each step.
- *Information reward* r_i , i.e. the predictive information between the past and current joint angle values.

In the reward function, the combination of the two distinct components is performed via a product rather than a sum, in order to prevent one term from dominating or being neglected during optimization. This multiplicative approach to reward shaping has been shown to be effective in previous work by Montufar et al. [9]. Additionally, the reward is transformed using a square function to suppress low values and emphasize higher ones. To properly handle negative values in the locomotion reward, the squared term is scaled by the sign of the locomotion component, ensuring consistent gradient direction. No such adjustment is required for the predictive information term, as it is intrinsically non-negative.

$$r_t = \text{sign}(r_{loc,t}) \cdot (|r_{loc,t}^\xi| r_{i,t}^{1-\xi})^2 \quad (4)$$

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section we provide and compare the results of the two different considered architectures.

A. WormBot I simulation

The described system has been implemented as two different modules communicating through standard sockets, namely i) the GP algorithm that has been implemented in Python exploiting the DEAP library [16], [17], [18], [19] and ii) the dynamics modeling and simulation relying on the ODE (Open Dynamics Engine) library [20], [21], implemented in C language. In our simulation runs we imposed a time

step duration equal to 0.05 s with 180 total time steps, and produced 40 generations, each comprising 200 individuals. We performed the simulations on an AMD Ryzen 7 7840HS, 3801 Mhz, 8 core, 16 logical processors computer, with an overall execution time of about 45 minutes. This time depends on different parameters, above all related to the genetic programming step, among which are the crossover and mutation probabilities (equal to 0.9 and 0.09 respectively). Figure 2 shows a screenshot of our worm-like robot during a simulation. During experimentation, we encountered significant challenges in steering the evolutionary process toward synchronized motion between the vertical and horizontal axes of the joints. Specifically, the evolved solutions often lacked coherent coordination across these axes, resulting in erratic or inefficient locomotion patterns. Due to these limitations and the inability to achieve satisfactory results with the evolutionary approach under the tested conditions, we have opted not to include detailed results from these experiments in this paper.

Fig. 2: Screenshot of the ODE-based system during a simulation run.

B. WormBot II simulation

For the experimental evaluation, each training run was conducted for a total of 10 million simulation steps. The simulation uses a timestep of 0.01 seconds, while control actions are applied every 0.1 seconds. To investigate the influence of the predictive information term on the emergence of behavior, we performed a parameter sweep over the weighting factor ξ , which scales the contribution of predictive information in the reward function. Specifically, we evaluated five values: $\xi = [0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0]$. This range spans from purely locomotion reward-driven learning ($\xi = 1.0$) to purely information reward-driven learning ($\xi = 0.0$). At each control step, predictive information is computed based on the previous 50 control steps, according to equation 1 ($\tau = 50$). This evaluation allows us to systematically assess how different levels of *information drive* affect the locomotion capabilities of the worm-like robot, and more broadly, to investigate the role of predictive information in shaping coordinated, self-organized movement in the absence of predefined motion primitives. The simulation are run on a 13th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-13900K, 5800Mhz, 24

Fig. 3: Reward values along WormBot II simulation.

core, 48 logical processor computer, coupled with a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090, with an overall execution time of 30 hours. Obtained rewards for the proposed scheme along the described simulation are depicted in Figure 3. We performed two different kinds of simulation, especially entrusting the demanding computation of the predictive information respectively to the CPU with the scikit-learn python library [22] and to the GPU employing the JAX python library [23]. Screenshots of the two simulations are depicted in Figure 4, which shows the emergence of a suitable locomotion behaviour for the WormBot, whose current positions are shown at time instants $t = [0, 12, 25, 37, 50, 62, 75, 87, 100]$ s.

The positive role of the predictive information term in the reward function is confirmed also by the computation of the *permutation entropy*, which indicates the eventual predictability within the data time series: this entropy decreases when the time series is more predictable given the past values. Figure 5 shows the mean of the all permutation entropies computed on all the WormBot joints. It is clear from the plot that there is a minimum in this entropy when a greater weight is assigned to the information-driven terms in the learning system reward function ($\xi = 0.25$), while the maximum value is reached in correspondence of purely locomotion reward-driven learning ($\xi = 1$).

To evaluate the temporal smoothness and coherence of the trajectories produced under different settings, we computed the autocorrelation [24] score for each condition. Specifically, we measured the autocorrelation of the time series data (e.g., joint angles' time series data) across 50 time lags, i.e. those used to compute the predictive information. Autocorrelation captures how well the values at one time point can be related to earlier values, and can therefore

be a preliminary proxy for smoothness or regularity in the signal. Figure 6 shows the autocorrelation scores for 3 adjacent joints, varied as a function of the parameter ξ . These examples were selected because they capture the overall temporal trend observed across all joints—every other joint follows a qualitatively similar pattern—so showing additional plots would be redundant. These results show a general trend: as ξ increases and predictive information decreases, the average autocorrelation scores across lags tends to drop. This indicates that the resulting behaviors become less temporally structured—i.e., less smooth or predictable over time. While this does not directly establish a causal relationship, it suggests that promoting predictive information during learning may be linked to the emergence of smoother, more temporally coherent motion patterns.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Our aim in this work was to investigate the emergence of a sensory motor coordination behaviors in a swarm of agents, and to explore the role of entropy-based information metrics in the emergence of suitable locomotion behaviors, specifically applied to a simple worm-like robot. We first built an architecture based on a classic Genetic Programming (GP) strategy and combining basic primitive functions to generate complex motion. After that, we explored the possibility to get rid of the predefined basic primitive functions in order to see if some coherent motion spontaneously emerged. The second version of the architecture we proposed confirmed that the WormBot is able to learn coherent locomotion patterns without any specific forcing of motion functions, only introducing a metrics related to predictive information, and thanks to the interaction of the agents (e.g. the worm

Fig. 4: Screenshots of the simulations for $\xi = 0.75$ at time instants $t = [0, 12, 25, 37, 50, 62, 75, 87, 100]$ s. (a)-(c), (g)-(i), (m)-(o): CPU-based predictive information computation, (d)-(f), (j)-(l), (p)-(r): GPU-based predictive information computation.

Fig. 5: Mean of the permutation entropy in all WormBot II joints computed versus the parameter ξ along the simulation.

nodes) among them. We developed a suitable learning system able to learn different motion models for the robot, maximizing the information metrics, and obtaining an individual able to move in a consistent way (in this case worm-wise) with the robot morphology. This should provide examples of intelligent behaviors through morphological computation and emergence from loosely coupled networks of embodied

agents.

In the future, we are planning to perform more simulation with the WormBot II architecture, to have a deeper insight on the system behaviour, and to obtain more statistically significant results to support the findings of our research activity, aiming to investigate the emergence of intelligent behaviors in networks of cooperating agents with distributed control. Further, we will focus on improving and optimizing the execution performance, to reduce the burden in terms of computational resources needed; to this aim, we will exploit a direct formulation of the predictive information that can be found in [2]. Moreover, we will also explore other information-related metrics to understand how the exchange of information in a network of embodied agents is related to the emergence of suitable behaviour.

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REFERENCES

- [1] I. Tanev, T. Ray, and A. Buller, “Automated evolutionary design, robustness, and adaptation of sidewinding locomotion of a simulated

Fig. 6: Autocorrelation of the joint angles' time series data across 50 time lags. The joints shown in the picture q_{h2} , q_{v2} , q_{v3} correspond to the second horizontal joint and to the second and third vertical joints. The autocorrelation is calculated for 50 time lags corresponding to the time instant used to calculate the predictive information ($\tau = 50$). The first score is omitted as it autocorrelates the timeseries with itself, so it provides no useful information.

- snake-like robot," *IEEE Transactions on robotics*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 632–645, 2005.
- [2] F. Bonsignorio, "Quantifying the evolutionary self-structuring of embodied cognitive networks," *Artificial life*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 267–289, 2013.
- [3] G. S. Chirikjian and J. W. Burdick, "A modal approach to hyper-redundant manipulator kinematics," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 343–354, 1994.
- [4] G. S. Chirikjian, *Stochastic Models, Information Theory, and Lie Groups, Volume 1: Classical Results and Geometric Methods*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2009.
- [5] G. S. Chirikjian and G. S. Chirikjian, "Information, communication, and group theory," *Stochastic Models, Information Theory, and Lie Groups, Volume 2: Analytic Methods and Modern Applications*, pp. 271–312, 2012.
- [6] M. Lungarella and O. Sporns, "Information self-structuring: Key principle for learning and development," in *Proceedings. The 4th International Conference on Development and Learning, 2005*. IEEE, 2005, pp. 25–30.
- [7] M. Lungarella, T. Pegors, D. Bulwinkle, and O. Sporns, "Methods for quantifying the informational structure of sensory and motor data," *Neuroinformatics*, vol. 3, pp. 243–262, 2005.
- [8] M. Prokopenko, V. Gerasimov, and I. Tanev, "Evolving spatiotemporal coordination in a modular robotic system," in *From Animals to Animals 9: 9th International Conference on the Simulation of Adaptive Behavior (SAB 2006) Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, S. Nolfi, G. Baldassarre, R. Calabretta, J. Hallam, D. Marocco, J. Meyer, O. Miglino, and D. Parisi, Eds., vol. 4095. Berlin–Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2007, pp. 558–569.
- [9] G. Montúfar, K. Ghazi-Zahedi, and N. Ay, "Information theoretically aided reinforcement learning for embodied agents," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1605.09735, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1605.09735>
- [10] F. Bonsignorio, "Preliminary considerations for a quantitative theory of networked embodied intelligence," in *Fifty years of AI*, M. Lungarella, F. Iida, J. Bongard, and R. Pfeifer, Eds. Berlin–Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2007.
- [11] W. Bialek, I. Nemenman, and N. Tishby, "Predictability, complexity and learning," 2001. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/physics/0007070>
- [12] A. J. Ijspeert, "Central pattern generators for locomotion control in animals and robots: A review," *Neural Networks*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 642–653, May 2008.
- [13] E. Todorov, T. Erez, and Y. Tassa, "Mujoco: A physics engine for model-based control," in *2012 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 5026–5033.
- [14] J. Schulman, F. Wolski, P. Dhariwal, A. Radford, and O. Klimov, "Proximal policy optimization algorithms," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1707.06347, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.06347>
- [15] A. Raffin, A. Hill, A. Gleave, A. Kanervisto, M. Ernestus, and N. Dormann, "Stable-baselines3: Reliable reinforcement learning implementations," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 22, no. 2688, pp. 1–8, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://jmlr.org/papers/v22/20-1364.html>
- [16] F.-M. De Rainville, F.-A. Fortin, M.-A. Gardner, M. Parizeau, and C. Gagné, "Deap: A python framework for evolutionary algorithms," in *Proceedings of the 14th annual conference companion on Genetic and evolutionary computation*, 2012, pp. 85–92.
- [17] —, "Deap: enabling nimbler evolutions," *ACM SIGEVOLUTION*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 17–26, 2014.
- [18] F.-A. Fortin, F.-M. De Rainville, M.-A. G. Gardner, M. Parizeau, and C. Gagné, "Deap: Evolutionary algorithms made easy," *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 2171–2175, 2012.
- [19] Anonymous, "Distributed evolutionary algorithms in python (deap) website," Accessed April 30, 2025, <https://deap.readthedocs.io/en/master/>.
- [20] R. Smith *et al.*, "Open dynamics engine," 2005.
- [21] Anonymous, "Open dynamics engine website," Accessed April 30, 2025, www.ode.org.
- [22] —, "Scikit-learn library website," Accessed April 30, 2025, <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>.
- [23] —, "Jax library website," Accessed April 30, 2025, <https://docs.jax.dev/en/latest/quickstart.html>.
- [24] Y. Dodge, *Autocorrelation*. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2008, pp. 24–26. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-32833-1_17